

Review report on extended abstract titled “The Claims Network: Aggregating Traditional & Non-Traditional Scholarly Contributions Using Mastodon”

Authors (alphabetically by last name)

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Feedback Reviewer 1 Andrea Mannocci

Reviewer 1					
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID4	5	4	5	5	Accept

This poster present Claim Network, a novel architecture based on social media platforms (Mastodon here) to track (the yet untracked) claims about Research, Education, Impact, and Leadership (REIL). The idea is compelling, and I reckon it falls nicely within the scope of the conference and GraspOS. I believe it can be of interest for the event and foster discussion around this theme. On site, I would be interested in understanding more about the gatekeeping/diffusion of potentially fake REIL claims in such a totally decentralised architecture.

Feedback Reviewer 2 Laurent Romary

Reviewer 2					
ID	Relevance	Significance	Novelty & Originality	Clarity & Quality of Presentation	Overall Judgement
ID4	5	3	4	4	Accept

The paper presents an interesting experiment integrating various types of academic production declaration. Although I can see the potential interest, I am missing the possible connection to a) existing information sources (publication, data etc. repositories) and b) existing aggregation portals or dashboards. Beyond mentioning RDF, nothing is said about the actual format (standard?) that is being used to interchange all these pieces of information.

